

Assessment of Fertility Characteristics and Family Planning Practices among Males in a Semi Urban Community, Southern Nigeria

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Fertility behavior and family planning practices are crucial for health and socioeconomic development in sub-Saharan Africa. In Nigeria, although awareness of family planning is high, contraceptive use remains low, particularly among men. This study examines fertility preferences, contraceptive use, and sociodemographic factors influencing these behaviors in Usen community, Edo State.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted in Usen, Ovia South-West Local Government Area, Edo State. A total of 427 men aged 18 years and older were selected using systematic sampling. Data were collected via a structured questionnaire on sociodemographics, fertility preferences, and contraceptive use. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize data, and chi-square tests assessed associations between variables. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: Of 400 respondents, 75% had children (mean = 3.23 ± 1.7). Forty-two percent desired more children (mean desired = 2.4 ± 1.2). Contraceptive use was reported by 69%, with all users relying on condoms. Marital status was significantly associated with fertility desire ($p = 0.048$, OR = 0.618), with married men more likely to desire more children. Education also influenced fertility desires ($p = 0.048$, OR = 1.619), with non-tertiary educated men more likely to want larger families. Contraceptive use was significantly higher among Christians (74.4%) compared to Muslims (46.7%) and adherents of African traditional religions (58.1%) ($p = 0.001$). Income was significantly associated with contraceptive use ($p = 0.002$, OR = 2.003), with lower-income men more likely to use contraception.

Conclusion: The study shows a shift toward smaller families in Usen, but cultural pressures and male-child preference persist. Despite high awareness, contraceptive use remains limited to condoms. Expanding access to various contraceptive methods and increasing male involvement in family planning could enhance reproductive health outcomes in rural Nigeria.

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INTRODUCTION:

Fertility behavior and family planning practices are central to population dynamics, maternal and child health, and socioeconomic development, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, where fertility levels remain high.¹ Nigeria is the most populous country in Africa, with a total fertility rate of about 5.3 births per woman and a modern contraceptive prevalence of roughly 12% among married women.² Rapid population growth, estimated at over 2.5% annually, continues to place pressure on household resources, health systems, and social infrastructure, especially in rural and semi-urban communities.^{2,3}

Family planning is a proven public health intervention that reduces unintended pregnancies, lowers maternal and infant mortality, and improves household economic stability.^{4,5} However, uptake of modern contraceptive methods in Nigeria remains low and uneven across regions, religions, and socioeconomic groups.⁶ Evidence suggests that while awareness of family planning is relatively high, consistent use is limited, with condoms being the most commonly used method and permanent methods such as vasectomy being extremely rare.^{7,8} One key factor underlying this pattern is the dominant role of men in fertility decision-making within households.

In many Nigerian communities, men largely determine family size, birth spacing, and whether contraception is acceptable, with studies showing that male preference for large families, concerns about reduced masculinity, religious beliefs, and economic considerations significantly influence fertility behaviour.^{8,9} Male involvement has been associated with higher contraceptive uptake and better reproductive health outcomes, yet men remain under-represented in family planning

research and interventions, which have historically focused on women.¹⁰

Edo State reflects these broader national patterns, with fertility preferences shaped by education, occupation, income, and religious affiliation. In communities such as Usen, where trading, farming, and artisanal work are common, children may be viewed as economic assets and social security, reinforcing preferences for higher fertility. At the same time, increasing levels of education and exposure to reproductive health information are gradually influencing attitudes toward smaller family sizes and modern family planning methods.

Despite the importance of male participation, there is limited community-level data on fertility characteristics and family planning practices among men in Edo State. This study, therefore, examines fertility preferences, contraceptive use, and associated sociodemographic factors among men in Usen community. The findings are expected to provide context-specific evidence to support male-inclusive family planning strategies, improve contraceptive acceptance, and contribute to healthier families and sustainable population management in the community.

MATERIAL AND METHOD:

Study Design, Setting, and Population: A community-based cross-sectional analytical study was conducted in Usen community, Ovia South-West Local Government Area of Edo State, Nigeria. Usen is a semi-urban agrarian settlement located between Benin City and Akure, with residents predominantly engaged in farming, trading, artisanal work, and civil service. Adult men aged 18 years and above residing in the community constituted the study population.

Sample Size and Sampling Procedure: The minimum sample size was determined using the

Cochran formula for single proportions, assuming a 49.3% prevalence of desire for more children among men, a 95% confidence level, and a 5% margin of error. This yielded a minimum sample size of 384, which was increased to 427 after adjusting for a 10% non-response rate. Systematic sampling was used to select households within the community, with an estimated sampling interval of two households. One eligible man was selected from each sampled household.

Data Collection and Study Variables: Data were collected using a structured interviewer-administered questionnaire adapted and refined for the local context. The instrument obtained information on respondents' sociodemographic characteristics, fertility history and preferences, contraceptive use, and perceived factors influencing fertility decisions. The primary outcome variables were the desire for more children and use of family planning/contraception. Independent variables included age, marital status, educational status, religion, occupation, household income, and fertility-related characteristics such as number of children and sex preference. The

questionnaire was pretested in a neighbouring community with similar characteristics, and necessary adjustments were made prior to the main survey.

Data Analysis and Presentation: Data were entered and analyzed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 27. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize variables using frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations. Associations between sociodemographic factors and both desire for more children and contraceptive use were assessed using the chi-square test. Odds ratios with 95% confidence intervals were computed where appropriate. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Results were presented using frequency tables and figures.

Ethical Considerations: Ethical approval was obtained from the relevant departmental ethics committee. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants, and confidentiality was ensured through anonymization of questionnaires and restricted data access. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were free to withdraw at any stage of the study.

RESULT:**Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics of respondents**

Variable	Frequency n = 400	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
18 - 30	120	30.0
31 - 40	160	40.0
41 - 50	76	19.0
>50	44	11.0
Mean ± S.D	37.21 ± 9.7	
Marital status		
Married	292	73.0
Single	96	24.0
Divorced/Separated	12	3.0
Educational Status		
No formal education	64	16.0
Primary education	84	21.0
Secondary education	156	39.0
Tertiary education	96	24.0
Religion		
Christianity	312	78.0
Islam	60	15.0
African traditional religion	28	7.0
Occupation		
Trader	116	29.0
Farmer	84	21.0
Artisan	80	20.0
Civil servant	76	19.0
Unemployed	44	11.0
Household income (₦)		
<20,000	100	25.0
20,000 – 50,000	152	38.0
50,001 – 100,000	92	23.0
>100,000	56	14.0

A total of 400 respondents were studied, with a mean age of 37.21 ± 9.7 years. The majority were aged 31–40 years (40.0%), followed by those aged 18–30 years (30.0%). Respondents aged 41–50

years accounted for 19.0%, while 11.0% were above 50 years.

Most respondents were married (73.0%), while 24.0% were single and 3.0% were divorced or

separated. Secondary education was the most common level of educational attainment (39.0%), followed by tertiary education (24.0%) and primary education (21.0%); 16.0% had no formal education.

Christianity was the predominant religion (78.0%), followed by Islam (15.0%) and African traditional religion (7.0%). Trading was the most common

occupation (29.0%), with farming (21.0%), artisanal work (20.0%), and civil service (19.0%) also represented; 11.0% were unemployed.

Regarding household income, 38.0% earned ₦20,000–₦50,000 monthly, 25.0% earned less than ₦20,000, 23.0% earned ₦50,001–₦100,000, and 14.0% earned above ₦100,000.

Table 2: Fertility Characteristics and Contraceptive Practices of Respondents

Variable	Frequency (n = 400)	Percentage (%)
Respondents with children		
Yes	300	75.0
No	100	25.0
Number of children (among those with children)		
Mean ± SD	3.23 ± 1.7	—
Desire to have more children		
Yes	168	42.0
No	232	58.0
Desired number of children (Mean ± SD)	2.4 ± 1.2	—
Preferred sex composition of children		
Equal number of both	152	38.0
No preference	148	37.0
More males than females	88	22.0
More females than males	12	3.0
Use of contraception		
Yes	276	69.0
No	124	31.0
Method of contraception used*		
Barrier method (e.g. condom)	276	69.0
Vasectomy/Others	0	0.0

Out of the 400 respondents, 300 (75.0%) had children, while 100 (25.0%) had none. Among respondents with children, the mean number of children was 3.23 ± 1.7. A total of 168 respondents (42.0%) expressed a desire to have more children,

whereas 232 (58.0%) did not. The mean desired number of children was 2.4 ± 1.2.

Regarding preferred sex composition, 152 respondents (38.0%) preferred an equal number of male and female children, 148 (37.0%) reported no sex preference, 88 (22.0%) preferred more males

than females, and 12 (3.0%) preferred more females than males. Contraceptive use was reported by 276 respondents (69.0%), while 124 (31.0%) were not using any method. All

respondents who reported contraceptive use relied on barrier methods such as condoms (69.0%), with no reported use of vasectomy or other methods

Figure 1: Perceived factors influencing fertility preference

Education was the most frequently reported factor influencing men's fertility decisions, identified by 212 respondents (53.0%). Societal pressure to have children soon after marriage and cultural practices influencing expected family size were each

reported by 180 respondents (45.0%). Family expectations determining the number of children were reported by 176 respondents (44.0%). Religion was reported as an influencing factor by 124 respondents (31.0%).

Table 3: Sociodemographic Factors Associated with Desire for More Children

Variable	Yes n = 168 (%)	No n = 232 (%)	p-value	OR (95% CI)
Age (years)				
< 30	48 (40.0)	72 (60.0)		
≥ 30	120 (42.9)	160 (57.1)		
$\chi^2 = 0.281$			0.596	0.889 (0.575–1.374)
Marital status				
Single	32 (33.3)	64 (66.7)		
Married/Separated	136 (44.7)	168 (55.3)		
$\chi^2 = 3.985$			0.048	0.618 (0.382–0.999)
Educational status				
Non-tertiary	136 (44.7)	168 (55.3)		
Tertiary	32 (33.3)	64 (66.7)		
$\chi^2 = 3.859$			0.048	1.619 (1.001–2.619)
Religion				
Christianity	136 (43.6)	176 (56.4)		
Islam	16 (26.7)	44 (73.3)		
African Traditional Religion	16 (57.1)	12 (42.9)		
$\chi^2 = 8.750$			0.013	—
Monthly income (₦)				
≤ 50,000	104 (41.3)	148 (58.7)		
> 50,000	64 (43.2)	84 (56.8)		
$\chi^2 = 0.149$			0.699	0.922 (0.612–1.391)

Desire for more children was reported by 168 respondents (42.0%), while 232 (58.0%) did not desire additional children. Among respondents aged below 30 years, 48 (40.0%) desired more children compared with 120 (42.9%) of those aged 30 years and above, with no significant association observed ($p = 0.596$).

With respect to marital status, 32 single respondents (33.3%) desired more children compared with 136 married or separated respondents (44.7%), and this association was statistically significant ($p = 0.048$). Regarding educational status, 136 respondents with non-

tertiary education (44.7%) expressed a desire for more children compared with 32 respondents with tertiary education (33.3%), also showing a significant association ($p = 0.048$).

By religion, 136 Christians (43.6%), 16 Muslims (26.7%), and 16 adherents of African traditional religion (57.1%) desired more children, with religion being significantly associated with fertility desire ($p = 0.013$). Monthly income showed no significant association, as 104 respondents earning ₦50,000 or less (41.3%) desired more children compared with 64 respondents earning above ₦50,000 (43.2%) ($p = 0.699$).

Table 4: Sociodemographic Factors Associated with Use of Family Planning/Contraception

Variable	Yes n = 276 (%)	No n =124 (%)	p- value	OR (95% CI)
Age (years)				
< 30	92 (76.7)	28 (23.3)		
≥ 30	184 (65.7)	96 (34.3)		
$\chi^2 = 4.711$			0.030	1.714 (1.050–2.788)
Marital status				
Single	64 (66.7)	32 (33.3)		
Married/Separated	212 (69.7)	92 (30.3)		
$\chi^2 = 0.322$			0.571	0.868 (0.532–1.417)
Educational status				
Non-tertiary	208 (68.4)	96 (31.6)		
Tertiary	68 (70.8)	28 (29.2)		
$\chi^2 = 0.198$			0.656	0.892 (0.540–1.474)
Religion				
Christianity	232 (74.4)	80 (25.6)		
Islam	28 (46.7)	32 (53.3)		
African Traditional Religion	16 (58.1)	12 (42.9)		
$\chi^2 = 20.020$			0.001	—
Monthly income (₦)				
≤ 50,000	188 (74.6)	64 (25.4)		
> 50,000	88 (59.5)	60 (40.5)		
$\chi^2 = 9.997$			0.002	2.003 (1.298–3.090)

Use of family planning was reported by 276 respondents (69.0%), while 124 (31.0%) were not using any contraceptive method. Among respondents aged below 30 years, 92 (76.7%) reported using family planning compared with 184 respondents aged 30 years and above (65.7%), and this association was statistically significant ($p = 0.030$).

With respect to marital status, 64 single respondents (66.7%) used family planning compared with 212 married or separated respondents (69.7%), with no statistically significant association observed ($p = 0.571$). Regarding educational status, 208 respondents with

non-tertiary education (68.4%) reported contraceptive use compared with 68 respondents with tertiary education (70.8%), and this association was not statistically significant ($p = 0.656$).

Religion was significantly associated with use of family planning ($p = 0.001$). Contraceptive use was reported by 232 Christians (74.4%), 28 Muslims (46.7%), and 16 adherents of African traditional religion (58.1%). Monthly income also showed a significant association, as 188 respondents earning ₦50,000 or less (74.6%) reported using family planning compared with 88 respondents earning above ₦50,000 (59.5%) ($p = 0.002$).

DISCUSSION:

The findings of this study indicate that fertility levels among men in Usen community remain high, with almost three-quarters of respondents already having children and the mean number of children exceeding the desired family size. This is consistent with studies from other rural Nigerian communities, where early childbearing, societal pressures and cultural norms contribute to larger family sizes than initially preferred.^{11, 12} In contrast, urban areas like Lagos report a growing trend towards smaller family sizes, attributed to higher education levels and improved access to family planning services.¹³ This discrepancy highlights the need for context-specific interventions in rural areas that can bridge the gap between desired and achieved fertility.

More than half of the respondents did not desire additional children, reflecting a gradual shift towards fertility limitation. This finding aligns with trends observed in a similar study conducted in Ekiti, Nigeria, where rising awareness of the economic costs and social implications of large families has led to preferences for smaller family sizes.¹⁴ However, despite this shift, cultural expectations and societal pressures continue to influence reproductive decisions, as demonstrated by the continued male-child preference in almost a quarter of respondents. Addressing these cultural preferences through targeted education campaigns could help mitigate unnecessary fertility driven by gender norms.

Contraceptive use was reported by almost seven in ten respondents, with all users relying on condoms, the most common male-controlled method. This pattern is consistent with other rural Nigerian studies, where barrier methods are the predominant choice.^{15, 16} The exclusive reliance on condoms in Usen indicates a limited method mix and a missed opportunity for broader male participation in family planning. Expanding awareness and

providing access to a variety of contraceptive options would help improve reproductive health outcomes.

Marital status, educational level, and religion were significantly associated with fertility desires. Married men were more likely to desire additional children, a finding that reflects the influence of marital expectations and familial pressures. This is consistent with studies from Osun and Niger state, where fertility is often seen as a marital duty.^{17, 18} Men with lower educational attainment were also more likely to want larger families, which is in line with studies showing that lower educational levels correlate with higher fertility desires, and urban areas with higher levels of education tend to report reduced fertility desires^{19, 20}. Religion also played a significant role, with Christian respondents showing higher contraceptive use compared to Muslims and adherents of African traditional religions. This finding supports research that shows reduced levels of contraceptive acceptance among certain religious groups, suggesting the need for faith-based family planning interventions.^{21, 22}

Age, income, and religion were associated with contraceptive use. Younger and lower-income men were more likely to use contraception, in contrast to a study carried out among nine African countries, where older, wealthier men tend to use contraception more.²³ Lower-income men in Usen were more likely to use contraception, possibly due to economic constraints that drive fertility regulation. This finding emphasizes the role of economic factors in shaping reproductive behaviour in rural communities, where lower-income households may view family planning as a necessary strategy to manage limited resources.

CONCLUSION:

This study highlights that while fertility preferences in Usen community are shifting toward smaller families, cultural norms and societal

pressures, such as male-child preference, continue to influence reproductive decisions. Despite high awareness of family planning, reliance on condoms as the only contraceptive method points to gaps in male engagement and contraceptive options. Addressing these issues through male-inclusive strategies and community-based interventions could improve reproductive health outcomes and contribute to sustainable population management.

LIMITATIONS:

The cross-sectional design of this study limits causal inference, and self-reported data may introduce response bias. To minimize these, the instrument was pretested and data collection was conducted by trained interviewers. The focus on a single community may limit generalizability, but the findings are valuable for similar rural settings. The study also didn't explore specific barriers to contraceptive use, particularly permanent methods, which warrant further investigation.

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Conflict of Interest:

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions:

All authors contributed to the conception, study design, analysis, drafting and approved the final manuscript.

Data Availability Statement:

The data supporting the findings are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

AI Use Declaration:

The authors declare that any AI tools used were limited to language assistance where applicable.

The authors remain fully responsible for the content.

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